

Prediction of Coolant Void Fraction and Temperature Distributions by Deep Neural Network in Coupled Multi-Physics Simulation of Boiling Water Reactor 8×8 Pin Bundle

Carren Liong^{1,*}, Tomohiro Endo¹, Kenichi Tada², Akio Yamamoto¹

¹Nagoya University, Nagoya, Aichi, Japan,

²Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Tokai-mura, Naka-gun, Ibaraki, Japan

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ABSTRACT

A Deep Neural Network (DNN) is applied to predicting pin-wise coolant void and temperature distributions in a BWR 8×8 bundle for the neutronics/thermal hydraulics multi-physics coupling simulation. The calculation results, obtained through precise neutronics and thermal hydraulics simulations on a Boiling Water Reactor (BWR) 8×8 bundle under with and without control blade inserted conditions, serve as the training data for the DNN model. In the DNN model, the pin-wise coolant void fraction and temperature radial distributions at the lower axial mesh, and the pin power radial distribution at the current axial mesh, are used to predict the coolant void fraction and temperature radial distributions at the current axial mesh. The DNN model makes accurate predictions for void fraction and temperature distributions at the no control blade case, although slight biases are observed in the blade insertion case.

Keywords: boiling water reactor, multi-physics analysis, subchannel analysis, machine learning, deep neural network

1. INTRODUCTION

Reactor simulation plays an important role in both conventional and new-generation nuclear reactor design, particularly in improving safety and efficiency. Advanced computational modeling is required for accurately predicting reactor core behavior; one such method is utilizing high-resolution multi-physics coupling simulations of neutronics and thermal hydraulics. Although coupled simulation provides high-fidelity results, it also requires a large amount of computational time and cost. The reduction of the computational cost is a significant challenge.

Previous research on multi-physics coupling simulations has been conducted extensively, especially in BWRs, which involve complex physical interactions between fuel rods and coolant water. For instance, Weber et al. [1, 2] coupled the 3D deterministic code DeCART with a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) code for reactor analysis, while Seker et al. [3] coupled the Monte Carlo code MCNP5 and a CFD code to a 3×3 Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) assembly. However, predicting the behavior of one assembly takes many hours, while full-core simulations take days or weeks. Therefore, accelerating multi-physics simulation is critical to addressing this issue, with machine learning approaches emerging as a promising solution.

Recent studies on multi-physics analysis have focused on the development and validation of reactor simulations while exploring ways to reduce computational costs [4]. O. Hennigh et al. [5] developed NVIDIA-based SimNet, an AI-accelerated multi-physics framework to solve the complex real-world multi-physics problem. Moreover, there has been a rapid increase in research applying machine

*ln-carren@fermi.energy.nagoya-u.ac.jp

learning techniques to accelerate reactor simulations [6]. Due to its ability to learn complex input-output relationships from simulation datasets, machine learning has demonstrated improvements in both accuracy and efficiency. For instance, Yamamoto [7] utilizes a neural network to predict the radial power distribution of PWR. J. J. Ortiz [8, 9] uses a neural network to predict core parameters in a BWR for optimizing refueling and then uses a multi-state recurrent neural network (RNN) to optimize the fuel loading patterns in the BWR core. F. Shriver [10] implements LatticeNet, a neural network based on computer vision, to predict the normalized pin powers and k_{eff} on PWR 17×17 pin fuel assembly. However, the prediction of pin-wise void fraction and temperature distributions in a BWR bundle with machine learning, using pre-calculated 3D pin-power, coolant void fraction, and temperature distributions, has not yet been extensively investigated as far as the authors' knowledge. Therefore, this research aims to apply machine learning techniques, such as Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), to predict void fraction and temperature distributions for neutronics and thermal-hydraulic (N-TH) coupling simulations of a BWR 8×8 bundle, particularly for the with and without control blade inserted bundle cases.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the N-TH simulation method and machine learning approach that will be utilized in Section 3. Section 3 focuses on numerical calculations as well as a discussion about the DNN model's capability in predicting void fraction and temperature distributions in a simple BWR 8×8 assembly. Lastly, the overall conclusion on the DNN approach and the future work to address current model limitations are summarized in Section 4.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Coupled Simulation of Boiling Water Reactor Simplified 8×8 Bundle.

In this study, GenesisRPC [11] and ACE-3D [12] are utilized to perform neutronics and thermal-hydraulics simulations, respectively. GenesisRPC, a general neutronics analysis code, was developed by implementing several features, e.g., including burnup calculations and effective cross-section evaluations, based on the Genesis code. Since GenesisRPC performs neutron transport calculation in 3D heterogeneous geometry, an accurate pin-power distribution can be obtained. The three-dimensional two-fluid model code, ACE-3D, developed by the Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA), employs a Lahey two-fluid model [13] to analyze the boiling phenomenon in generic conditions, including BWR assemblies. Unlike many subchannel codes, ACE-3D adopts a precise fluid analysis model that is suitable for a high-resolution multi-physics simulation. Using these two independent codes, the coupling simulation is performed by exchanging the necessary data.

Since GenesisRPC and ACE-3D simulate different physics phenomena, the mesh is also divided differently. In GenesisRPC, the temperature and void fraction are given for the resolution of the fuel cell, resulting in 64 in-channel and 36 out-channel regions for an 8×8 fuel bundle. It is noted that a fuel cell is radially divided into 12 flux regions in the neutronics simulation. The axial direction is divided into 28 meshes, including 2 top and 2 bottom reflector meshes. ACE-3D employs fine meshes to solve the effects of cross-flow between fuel rods. It uses 4 meshes for each fuel pin and 240 axial meshes (ten times finer than GenesisRPC axial meshes). ACE-3D does not model out-channel, top, and bottom reflector regions.

The coupling between GenesisRPC and ACE-3D is carried out by exchanging data that are shown in Figure 1. First, GenesisRPC performs neutronics calculations and obtains relative fission rates per fuel pin. These rates are then normalized by a fuel rod heat generation density (0.16 GW/m^3) and transferred to ACE-3D. Since ACE-3D uses a finer mesh, the heat source from a fuel rod obtained in GenesisRPC is distributed over 4 radial sub-meshes and 10 sub-meshes of ACE-3D.

Next, ACE-3D performs a thermal-hydraulics simulation, resulting in void fraction and coolant temperature distribution. These results are then mapped back to the coarser mesh in GenesisRPC by averaging 4 radial and 10 axial sub-mesh values of ACE-3D. These coupling procedures are repeated until the results in each simulation are converged.

Figure 1. Coupling calculation procedure between GenesisRPC and ACE-3D.

2.2. Machine Learning Application to Coupling Simulation

2.2.1. Deep neural network

BWR core simulations are complex due to the coupled, non-linear feedback between neutronics and thermal hydraulics. The thermal hydraulics parameters, such as void fraction (coolant density) and moderator temperature, affect neutron cross-sections and finally change the pin power distribution. Predicting this high-dimensional, non-linear relationship is a significant computational challenge. While two-phase flow simulations can precisely calculate the coolant void fraction and temperature distributions for each bundle, the high computational time presents a major challenge. Therefore, a DNN is utilized as a high-fidelity surrogate model to predict the desired outcomes using designated inputs from the coupling calculation.

Neural networks are used to capture complex, non-linear data relationships by updating the weights and biases that connect each layer. In the context of reactor physics, the pin-by-pin and subchannel distributions within each assembly create highly localized and similar patterns. These patterns can be analyzed by the DNN model to predict the coupled state, which bypasses the thermal-hydraulics simulation within the multi-physics calculation loop.

2.2.2. Applying neural network model to N-TH coupling simulations

DNN models were developed to utilize thermal-hydraulics and neutronics results generated from the coupling calculations [14]. In this implementation, the DNN model performs sequential predictions from a lower axial mesh to an upper axial mesh. Specifically, the DNN model uses coolant void fraction and temperature distributions of the lower axial mesh ($i - 1$) combined with the pin-power heat generation at the current axial mesh (i) as the input, to predict the void fraction and temperature distributions at the current axial mesh (i) as the output. This method captures the sequential thermal-hydraulic feedback along the coolant flow in a fuel bundle.

The DNN model handles three types of input data: pin-power distribution of axial mesh i , void fraction distribution of axial mesh ($i - 1$), and temperature distribution of axial mesh ($i - 1$). These input data are originally arranged as two-dimensional arrays having the size of (J, K) where J and K are the number of rows and columns of the fuel pin array in a bundle. These input data are rearranged into three sets of one-dimensional arrays of size $[J \times K]$. The output data, which consist of void fraction and temperature distribution of axial mesh (i), are arranged into two sets of one-dimensional arrays of size $[J \times K]$.

2.2.3. DNN architecture and learning procedure

The architecture of DNN is shown in Figure 2. The training procedures of the DNN model are as follows.

- (1) Three types of two-dimensional data, pin power (axial mesh i), void fraction (mesh $i - 1$), and temperature distribution (mesh $i - 1$) are flattened into one-dimensional data.
- (2) The target data are set from the void fraction distribution (axial mesh i) and the temperature distribution (mesh i).
- (3) The input data is provided to the input layer of the DNN model. The input layer consists of three types of radial distribution data (pin power, void fraction, temperature). The size of input is $[3 \times J \times K]$.
- (4) The entire dataset is normalized within 0 to 1 for each type of data.
- (5) Then the entire input data is divided into small sets, each consisting of $[3 \times J \times K]$, for each axial mesh.
- (6) The output training data is divided into small sets, each consisting of $[2 \times J \times K]$, for each axial mesh, representing the void fraction and temperature distributions at the axial mesh.
- (7) DNN is trained using input and output data.

The predicted results by DNN are then mapped back to the bundle assembly, and the normalized data are converted to the original (physical) values.

Moreover, the DNN model implements the hyperparameters as follows: number of iterations (epoch), batch size, and learning rate are set respectively as 1000, 1, 0.0001 (for epochs before 200) and 0.00001 (for epochs after 200).

Figure 2. Deep Neural Network for Predicting Coolant Void Fraction and Temperature.

3. NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

3.1. Calculation Conditions

The simulation target is a simplified 8×8 BWR fuel bundle, as shown in Figure 3. The specifications are based on the OECD/NEA Benchmark IIIB [15], but without the water rod. The fuel rods contain uranium dioxide (UO_2), which is wrapped in a zircaloy cladding. Here, the UO_2 enrichment is set at 1.63wt% uniformly throughout the bundle. The entire bundle and outer region of the channel box are filled with coolant light water. The outer channel water is not included in the ACE-3D, while it is considered in GenesisRPC. The 70 group cross section library based on JENDL-5 [16] is used, and the transport calculation is carried out by the LEAF method [17]. The temperature of the outer channel water is assumed to be unchanged in the bundle, which is identical to that of the inlet temperature. The inflow coolant pressure, temperature, and velocity are 7.07 MPa, 549.3 K, and 2.15 m/s, respectively. The total bundle power is 4.6 MW, which corresponds to 71,875 W per single fuel rod. In GenesisRPC, the bottom and top reflectors are considered. The boundary conditions for GenesisRPC are the vacuum condition for the bottom and top surfaces of the reflector, the reflective condition for the radial surface (outside of the outer channel water). The thermal and fluid boundary conditions for ACE-3D are constant temperature at the bottom, insulation (zero heat flux) at the top and sides of the channel; slip boundary condition at the channel box (channel box wall) surface to account for wall friction.

The simulation results of GenesisRPC are edited as follows: $2+24+2=28$ axial meshes (2 meshes for each reflector on top and bottom), $(8+2)\times(8+2)$ meshes in the radial direction (2 meshes for the channel box and outer channel water). The simulation results of ACE-3D are edited as follows: 240 axial meshes (top and bottom reflectors are not considered), $(8\times 2)\times(8\times 2)$ meshes in the radial direction (fuel cells are divided into 2×2).

Since ACE-3D is a time-dependent fluid analysis code, calculation of 6 seconds in physical simulation time (not computation time) is carried out to obtain a steady-state condition of coolant. In GenesisRPC, analyses are carried out by the k_{eff} -eigenvalue calculation assuming the steady state condition.

To demonstrate the capabilities of the DNN model, the analysis results of coupled multi-physics calculations by GenesisRPC and ACE-3D are used. Specifically, the converged data from the fifth coupling iteration results are utilized to train and validate the DNN model. For the verification of the DNN model, cross validation is used, as the data is divided into 70% for training and 30% for validation.

Figure 3. Simplified 8×8 BWR Bundle.

3.2. Results and Discussions

First, the DNN model is employed to predict the pin-wise void fraction and temperature distributions on the with and without control blade cases. The validation error of the DNN model, calculated with the normalized input/output data, is shown in Table I. The DNN model shows small Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) in predicting the radial distribution. However, the MAE and RMSE errors for the control blade inserted bundle case are higher, indicating model limitations in predicting the bundle's distribution under control blade insertion.

To further verify the model's accuracy, the correlation between the test and predicted data is plotted. Figures 4 and 6 present quantitative comparisons of the assembly distribution using scatter plots, while Figures 5 and 7 provide the qualitative comparisons based on the axially averaged assembly distribution. Figure 4 shows the scatter plot for the bundle case without control blade inserted. Here, the test and predicted data represent the reference data used for DNN training and the predicted data by DNN, respectively. In Figure 4, the void fraction exhibits small biases near 0.0 to 0.2, while the temperature displays small biases near 560 K in both predicted data. Despite these slight discrepancies, the model accurately captures the overall distribution patterns within the bundle. Figure 5 presents the predicted void fraction and temperature radial distributions for the bundle case without control blade inserted, averaged axially. The upper and lower values show the test and predicted values, respectively. Because the bundle does not include a water rod, both the void fraction and temperature distributions are lower in the center region.

The comparison with the control blade inserted bundle case is shown in Figure 6. It is noted that DNN is independently trained from the case without the control blade insertion. The void fraction distribution is predicted accurately; however, the model fails to fully capture the coolant temperature behavior. Specifically, the predicted temperature distribution differs from the reference data trend near 560 K. Further investigation is necessary to analyze the relationships among power, void fraction, and temperature distributions under the control blade inserted case. Figure 7 illustrates the predicted and

reference void fraction and temperature distributions (axial average) for the control blade inserted bundle case. In the region adjacent to the inserted control blade, both void fraction and temperature show lower values, while higher values appear on the opposite side. The DNN model effectively captures such features that appear in the axial average distribution across the bundle.

Table I. Summary of DNN Model Error.

	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)
Void Fraction (Without Control Blade)	3.3×10^{-3}	4.9×10^{-3}
Temperature (Without Control Blade)	3.3×10^{-3}	5.2×10^{-3}
Void Fraction (With Control Blade)	4.7×10^{-3}	1.1×10^{-2}
Temperature (With Control Blade)	4.6×10^{-3}	1.4×10^{-2}

Figure 4. Comparison between Test and Predicted Data Without Control Blade Case.

Figure 5. Predicted and Test Void and Temperature Data on Radial Position Without Control Blade Case. (the upper value means predicted value and the lower value means test value, axially averaged).

Figure 6. Comparison between Test and Predicted Data With Control Blade Inserted Case.

Figure 7. Predicted and Test Void and Temperature Data on Radial Position With Control Blade Inserted Case. (the upper value means predicted value and the lower value means test value, axially averaged).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study successfully demonstrates that a DNN model is capable of predicting the void fraction and coolant temperature distributions in a BWR single bundle. By using data generated from GenesisRPC and ACE-3D coupling simulations, the DNN model is trained on with and without control blade cases for BWR 8x8 bundles. The numerical results show the ability of the DNN model to learn the complex, non-linear relationships between pin power and coolant sub-channel distributions. The DNN model can also predict the highly localized relationships affected by the control blade, suggesting its potential use for accelerating N-TH simulations.

Despite the promising results, a key limitation of the current implementation remains in its supervised model. If a new case, for example, a different case with a half- or quarter-inserted control blade, is encountered, the new DNN model would have to be created to capture the new correlation. This dependency limits the model's ability to be used for new cases without additional training.

To address these limitations, future work will be expanded to include different controlled bundle cases (half or quarter-inserted blades) to test the model's accuracy across various reactor states.

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